

IMPLEMENTATION OF HALO CAPIL SERVICES IN POPULATION ADMINISTRATION SERVICES IN PADANG LAWAS REGENCY

Yulia Rahmadani Hrp *¹, Ti Aisyah², Risna Dewi³, Maulidi⁴, Muhammad Hasyem⁵

^{1,2,3,4} Universitas Malikussaleh Lhokseumawe -North Aceh , 081265341387

³ Department of Public Administration, Universitas Malikussaleh, Lhokseumawe

email: ¹ yulia.210210107@mhs.unimal.ac.id, ² tiaisyah@unimal.ac.id, ³ risna.dewi@unimal.ac.id ⁴ maulidi@unimal.ac.id ⁵

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Abstract

Population administration services are crucial public services because they directly relate to the provision of citizens' civil rights. In an effort to improve the quality and effectiveness of services, the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency has launched the Halo Capil Service as a technology-based service innovation through the WhatsApp application. This service provides easy access to information and facilitates the submission of population documents such as Family Cards and birth certificates. However, its implementation has not been optimal, primarily due to a lack of clear information and minimal outreach, resulting in rural communities not understanding the service's purpose and benefits. This study aims to describe the implementation of the Halo Capil Service in population administration services in Padang Lawas Regency. The research method used is descriptive qualitative with data collection techniques through interviews, observation, and documentation. The research analysis refers to the Edward III policy implementation model, which includes aspects of communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The results show that service implementation has not been optimal due to limited human resources, network constraints, and a lack of outreach and infrastructure support.

Keywords: Implementation, Halo Capil, Population Administration Services.

INTRODUCTION

Policy implementation is an activity carried out after the official direction of a policy or service has been established, encompassing efforts to manage inputs to produce outputs and outcomes in accordance with established objectives. Implementation is a crucial stage in the public policy process because it determines the policy's success in addressing public problems (Winarno in Marwiyah, 2022). Policy implementation is also understood as a complex process involving various actors, organizations, procedures, and techniques in the implementation of public policy. Population administration is part of the state administration system and plays a crucial role in governance and development. This system not only guarantees citizens' administrative rights but also raises public awareness of the obligation to report population-related events and provides statistical data necessary for development planning and improving the quality of public services in a fair and non-discriminatory manner. Therefore, population registration and civil registration, as part of population administration, need to be managed optimally.

Advances in information technology are driving government agencies to transform from conventional work systems to digital-based service systems. This change impacts the bureaucracy's perspective and work methods in providing more effective and efficient public services (Fatkhur et al., 2023). In line with this, Law Number 24 of 2013 concerning the Implementation of Population Administration requires every citizen to report population-related events to the implementing agency. Furthermore, Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 29 of 2019 emphasizes the implementation of the Population Administration Information System (SIAM) as part of e-Government in managing population data based on information technology. As a form of public service innovation, the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency has implemented the Halo Capil Service since 2018. This service aims

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to help the public obtain information and process population administration documents digitally, especially for people living in remote areas and far from service centers. The Halo Capil service is implemented via WhatsApp using systems and procedures established by the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency. However, based on initial observations and interviews with Halo Capil service operators, the service's implementation has not been optimal. Several issues identified include service procedures that do not comply with Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), a convoluted service flow, relatively long service completion times, and the requirement for residents to bring physical documents when collecting them (Initial interview, October 22, 2024). Furthermore, some residents still do not understand the purpose and benefits of Halo Capil due to a lack of public awareness, particularly in remote areas (Ismawati, 2023).

Table 1
Number of Halo Capil Service User Data in 2023 (via WhatsApp)

N O	Document Type	Amount
1	Family Card (KK)	727
2	Resident Identity Card (KTP)	1041
3	Child Identity Card (KIA)	0
4	Certificate of Moving	98
5	Birth certificate	355
6	Death Certificate	33
Total		2,254

Data source: Padang Lawas Regency Population and Civil Registry Office (2025)

Based on table 1.1 is a list of the number of people who use the Halo Capil Service in managing population administration such as family cards, resident identity cards, child identity cards, moving certificates, birth certificates, death certificates in 2023 as many as 2,254 people, this shows that there are still very few people who have not activated or identified their population related to the use of the Halo Capil Service, especially for remote areas far from the Padang Lawas Regency Population and Civil Registration Office. This situation indicates that the implementation of digital services has not been fully accepted and utilized optimally by the public. The mismatch between established procedures and field practices, as well as the public's low level of understanding, has the potential to hinder the government's goal of providing easy, fast, and efficient population administration services. Therefore, this study aims to analyze and describe the implementation of the Halo Capil service in population administration services at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Public service

Public services essentially encompass the entire process of meeting the needs of the community, both in the narrow sense of direct interaction between government officials and the community, and in the broader sense encompassing the basic needs of the community as a whole. Public services are not limited to administrative services, but also encompass government efforts to create orderly, safe, and prosperous living conditions for the community. A similar view is expressed by Grönroos (1990:27) who states that services are intangible activities or series of activities that arise from interactions between service users and service providers. Along with the dynamics of community needs, the public service paradigm continues to evolve towards more efficient, responsive, and community-oriented services. Service quality is determined by several key factors, as stated by Parasuraman in Zaenal (2015:215), including reliability, responsiveness, competence, access, and communication. These five factors are important indicators in assessing the success of public services, particularly in administrative services that demand accuracy, speed, and clarity of information.

Public Policy

Public policy is a government decision to take or not take action aimed at addressing public problems. Thomas, in Agustino (2006:87), explains that public policy encompasses government choices based on considerations of benefits for the common good. Meanwhile, Richard, in Agustino (2006:112), views public policy as a series of interrelated activities that have consequences for stakeholders. Thus, public policy can be understood as a government strategy formulated systematically and implemented based on laws and regulations.

Policy Implementation

Policy implementation is a crucial stage in the public policy cycle, namely the process of implementing policy decisions so that they can be translated into concrete actions in the field. Hupe in Ramadhan (2016:105) emphasizes that policy implementation is not simply the application of decisions, but rather a complex process that requires planning, resource allocation, and the involvement of various actors. Wahab in Abdoellah (2016:115) adds that implementation focuses on what actually happens after the policy is established, including administrative activities and their impact on society. Gaffar (2009:97) also states that implementation is a series of activities to convey policies to the public so that policy objectives can be achieved. In this study, policy implementation is explained based on George C. Edward III's relevant and comprehensive theory. Edward III, in Abdoellah (2016:120), proposed four variables that influence the success of policy implementation: communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure. These four variables are interrelated in determining the effectiveness of service implementation, particularly in the context of service products, service requirements, and service procedure mechanisms (Agustino, 2006).

Policy Implementation Models and Factors

Edward III in Abdoellah (2016:215) emphasized that clear communication, resource availability, implementer commitment, and the credibility of the structure supported by SOPs are key to successful policy implementation. Furthermore, Charles O. Jones (1996:296) outlined three main activities in policy implementation: organization, interpretation, and implementation, emphasizing the importance of resource management, clarity of policy direction, and operational support. The success of policy implementation is also influenced by supporting and inhibiting factors. Warwick in Mulyadi (2018:108) distinguishes between factors that drive and inhibit implementation, such as leadership commitment, organizational capacity, and support from implementing groups. Van Meter and Van Horn in Agustino (2006:272) add that implementation performance is influenced by the size and objectives of the policy, resources, characteristics of the implementing organization, implementer attitudes, inter-organizational communication, and the social, economic, and political environment. Conversely, implementation barriers can stem from internal and external factors, such as limited resources, weaknesses in policy content, and unfavorable environmental conditions (Morss in Pasolong, 2010).

Population Administration and Halo Capil Services

Population administration is a series of activities for organizing and collecting population documents through population registration and civil registration as regulated in Law Number 23 of 2016. Population administration functions to guarantee the administrative rights of residents, provide population data, and support public services and development. Population administration services include the collection of important documents such as KTP, KK, and Civil Registration certificates, which play a role in guaranteeing the identity and civil rights of citizens (Mariati, 2017). The Halo Capil service is an innovative population administration service implemented by the Padang Lawas Regency Population and Civil Registration Office through the WhatsApp application. This service aims to simplify the process of managing population documents, especially for those in remote areas. The Halo Capil service focuses on service products, service requirements, and service mechanisms and procedures, which are expected to improve the accessibility, efficiency, and quality of public services.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach to analyze the implementation of the Halo Capil service in population administration services, including factors and obstacles. This approach was chosen because the research was conducted in natural settings with the researcher as the primary instrument, the data collected was descriptive, and the analysis was conducted inductively, emphasizing the meaning of the phenomenon under study (Sugiyono, 2021). The

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research data consisted of primary data obtained through direct observation and in-depth interviews with informants selected intentionally and unintentionally, as well as secondary data sourced from official documents and relevant references. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation, interviews, and documentation, while data analysis was carried out through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions to obtain a comprehensive picture of the implementation of the Halo Capil Service and the problems faced in population administration services (Sugiyono, 2021).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Halo Capil Service Overview

The Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency is an implementing agency for population administration services located in the Sigalagala Integrated SKPD Office Complex, with the main task of providing population services such as KTP, KK, birth certificates, death certificates, and other population documents. The Halo Capil service innovation via WhatsApp was developed as a service digitalization strategy to speed up the process, expand reach, and reduce queues at the office, in line with the vision of "Realizing Prime Population Administration Services".

Table 2
Population of Padang Lawas Regency

NO	District,	Male ²	PR	Total population
1	Politeness	5,467	5,410	10,877
2	Ulu Barumun	8,898	8,851	17,749
3	Barumun	21,075	21,876	43,681
4	South Barumun	4,254	4,163	8,417
5	New Barumun	6,539	6,556	13,095
6	Barumun Lake	10,898	10,615	21,513
7	Sosa	10,527	10,545	21,072
8	Ulu Sosa	4,709	4,672	9,470
9	Sosa Julu	5,535	5,565	11,100
10	Lubu Sutam River	4,167	4,197	8,364
11	High King's Hut	20,702	20,221	40,923
12	East Sosa	4,542	4,254	8,796
13	Huristak	9,665	9,362	19,027
14	Central Barumun	8,442	8,446	16,888
15	Aek Nabara Barumun	7,042	6,993	14,035
16	Sihapas Barumun	2,942	3,071	6,117
17	West Barumun	2,269	2,255	4,524
Total		155,619,190 (souls)		

Source: Data from BPS Padang Lawas Regency

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Padang Lawas Regency's population is spread across 17 sub-districts, with a total population of 155,619,190, according to the BPS data used in this study. Its geographical location, encompassing highland areas and remoteness from city centers, provides a crucial context for the use of internet-based services such as Halo Capil.

Implementation of Halo Capil Services

Interviews with the Secretary of the Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil), operators, village officials, community leaders, and residents revealed that Halo Capil allows the public to manage several types of services, particularly the issuance and amendment of Family Cards (KK), birth certificates, death certificates, and marriage and divorce certificates. In addition to documents, the channel is also used for consultations on requirements, checking application status, and submitting complaints via WhatsApp. Procedurally, the service flow includes initiating contact to an official number, selecting the type of service, sending photos or scanned documents, checking for initial completeness, verifying data, processing documents, and producing results in either digital or physical files. The Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil) has developed Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that regulate the service flow, communication formats, response times, verification data, and document management mechanisms to maintain consistency, accountability, and ease of auditing.

DISCUSSION

Implementation of Halo Capil Services in Population Administration Services at the Population and Civil Registration Service of Padang Lawas Regency.

The implementation of the Halo Capil service in population administration and civil registration services in Padang Lawas Regency is a strategic step to improve the quality of public services. Through the Halo Capil service, the Civil Registration and Population Administration Agency (Dukcapil) has boldly utilized technology to expedite the population administration process. The integrated Population Administration Information System (SIAK) is efficient and transparent.

a. Product Services

Service products in public administration are non-physical forms of service provided by government agencies to meet the rights and needs of the public, such as ease of access, speed of processing, and clarity. One such service innovation is Halo Capil via WhatsApp, developed by the Population and Civil Registration Service (Disdukcapil). Based on an interview with the Secretary of the Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil), the Halo Capil service allows the public to access various population administration services without having to visit the office in person. Services provided include issuing and amending Family Cards (KK), birth certificates, death certificates, marriage and divorce certificates, as well as consultations regarding requirements, document status monitoring, and filing complaints. This service aims to improve the speed and convenience of service, especially for people with limited time and distance.

The implementation of Halo Capil services is supported by Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), which regulates service flow, communication formats, response times, data verification, and document management mechanisms. This SOP serves to maintain consistency, accountability, and service security, while also ensuring that services via WhatsApp have the same administrative authority as other official channels. From a user perspective, the public finds the Halo Capil service very helpful because it saves time, money, and effort. The service information is considered clear and easy to understand, especially since officers use simple language and get to the point. The service is also considered effective in reducing queues at Disdukcapil offices and increasing the efficiency of public services.

However, interviews also revealed challenges in service implementation, particularly related to digital literacy disparities and limited internet access for some communities, particularly the elderly and residents in areas with unstable networks. Furthermore, information on the service is not yet fully distributed, resulting in not all community groups understanding and optimally utilizing it. In relation to Edward III's policy implementation theory, the communication aspect of Halo Capil service information transmission still needs improvement to make it more equitable and inclusive. While the service is generally considered positive and innovative, optimizing communication strategies, community support, and strengthening synergies with village governments are crucial to ensuring that Halo Capil services are accessible and utilized by all levels of society in a fair and effective manner.

b. Terms of Service

The requirements for the Halo Capil service are clearly structured and adhere to the Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for population service administration. These requirements cover completeness, document completion, and verification, as well as the delivery mechanism for service results. Information requirements are communicated through various media, such as WhatsApp, brochures, written guides, and information boards, using relatively simple language to ensure public understanding, depending on the type of service provided, such as ID cards (KTP), family cards (Kartu Keluarga), and civil registration certificates. However, the interview results show that there are variations in people's understanding. Service requirements. Those with experience in administrative matters tend to have an easier time understanding and meeting requirements, while new applicants, the elderly, and those with limited digital literacy or internet access often struggle with document details and procedural steps. This can lead to incomplete documents, slow processing times, and the need for repeated verification or additional permits by officers. In practice, Halo Capil officers conduct an initial check of the completeness of documents submitted by the public via photos or scans before further processing applications. This mechanism serves as quality control to ensure that incoming applications meet administrative requirements. However, field findings also indicate the need for improved communication and outreach strategies to ensure that information on requirements is not only available but also truly understood. Referring to Edward III's policy implementation theory, the communication aspect still needs to be strengthened through more detailed guidelines, written confirmation after consultation, and a more inclusive outreach approach to ensure that Halo Capil services can be effectively accessed by all levels of society.

c. System Mechanism and Procedure

In terms of mechanisms and procedures, officials and residents acknowledged that written procedures were clearly structured and communicated via WhatsApp messages, making them easy for users to review. However, reliance on WhatsApp and digital technology creates challenges for the elderly, residents in areas with weak signal reception, and those unfamiliar with sending digital documents. Therefore, village-level assistance and more systematic outreach are needed.

Implementation of Barriers Based on Edward III's Theory

Referring to the Edward III framework, the findings of the display show barriers in four variables, namely communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure.

1. Communication

Halo Capil services are not yet fully recognized in remote areas due to limited information, internet access, and digital literacy, despite ongoing outreach efforts through social media, banners, brochures, and word-of-mouth communication in villages. Village officials and community leaders believe that outreach remains unstructured, leaving many residents unclear about how to access the service and its requirements. This situation requires a more intensive, face-to-face, and comprehensive communication strategy, down to the village level.

2. Resource

In terms of infrastructure, unstable internet connections in highland areas and remote urban areas hinder the equitable use of Halo Capil. Furthermore, aging computer equipment, limited technological capacity, and network disruptions during peak hours slow down service processes and reduce the expected efficiency of digital services.

3. Disposition

In terms of attitude, implementers considered the Halo Capil concept a good innovation and demonstrated a commitment to serving the public, as evidenced by its simplicity, simple language, and willingness to provide repeated explanations. However, the congested workload on a single operator caused the data input process to take a significant amount of time, potentially delaying document completion and failing to meet the time standards set in the SOP. This situation indicates that individual commitment is not fully supported by organizational capacity.

4. Bureaucratic Structure

The Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil)'s organizational structure essentially has a clear division of duties, but coordination between departments in the implementation of Halo Capil has not been optimal. Some departments still operate separately, resulting in slow service delivery. Reliance on a single operator without backup staff and technical assistance indicates a low level of internal infrastructure readiness to support digital services and poses a risk of service interruption if the operator is unable to attend.

Relationship with Previous Research and Implications

The findings regarding communication barriers align with Rahma's (2023) research, which emphasized that a lack of effective outreach and low public literacy are key factors hindering the implementation of digital-based population administration services. The limited infrastructure network found in Padang Lawas Regency also supports Anisa's (2023) research, which states that the disparity in digital infrastructure hinders the optimal digitalization of population services. In terms of implementer disposition, the condition of only one operator handling the Halo Capil service confirms Oktapiya's (2023) findings regarding low collective commitment, implementer empathy, and internal organizational support that directly impact the quality of service implementation. Therefore, to optimize the implementation of the Halo Capil Service based on Edward III's theory, improvements are not enough to focus only on the technological system aspect, but also require strengthening public communication strategies, expanding network infrastructure, adding and training human resources, and structuring more integrative coordination across sectors and at the village level.

CLOSING

Conclusion

Based on the results of research conducted in the field regarding the implementation of Halo Capil Services in Population Administration Services at the Population and Civil Registration Service of Padang Lawas Regency, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. Implementation of the Halo Capil service at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency. Based on the implementation aspect, which focuses on service products, service requirements, and system mechanisms and procedures, it was found that the service is not fully optimized. Existing service products are still not fully accessible because the information provided to the public is not clearly conveyed. Service requirements are still considered confusing, and sometimes additional requirements are not included in the initial procedures. Document completion times also often do not comply with established SOPs, resulting in the service being deemed ineffective.
2. The obstacles in the implementation of Halo Capil Services in Population Administration Services at the Population and Civil Registration Office of Padang Lawas Regency are: The expected communication has not run optimally, the dissemination of information about Halo Capil Services is still very limited. Dispositional obstacles in the implementation of Halo Capil Services in Population and Civil Registration Services of Padang Lawas Regency can be seen in the low motivation, low role and low commitment of implementers in handling Halo Capil services. The next obstacle is the bureaucratic structure that is not optimal, minimal coordination and dependence on one individual who runs or handles this Halo Capil Service has not run optimally. This problem shows the weakness of the institutional foundation in supporting the digital transformation of the Population and Civil Registration Office.

Suggestion

1. Further research is recommended to use a quantitative approach or mixed method to measure the level of satisfaction and effectiveness of Halo Capil Services more objectively.
2. Future researchers can expand the study by adding variables of digital community literacy, human resource readiness, or quality of communication services in the implementation of digital population services.
3. It is also recommended that research be conducted in other areas or regions as a comparative study to obtain a broader picture of the implementation of similar services.

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